

Brain Stroke Prediction Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— The human brain, which controls our actions, thoughts, emotions, and bodily processes, is a fascinating illustration of the intelligence and complexity of the human body. However, it is not immune to flaws, with strokes being a major worry. When the blood supply to a portion of the brain is interrupted, it can result in a stroke, sometimes known as a "brain attack," which can have serious implications, including long-term neurological impairment and, in some circumstances, death. Early stroke detection is given the utmost emphasis in this study because it can significantly lessen the severity of its effects. Early intervention can drastically change how a stroke develops, thereby reducing long-term consequences. The study combines machine learning and deep learning methods. An accurate dataset obtained from Kaggle, a renowned data science site, was used to evaluate the performance of the created method. Decision Tree is the algorithm used in the study. It should be noted that the Decision Tree method, with a stunning score of 90.13 percent, displayed the accuracy.

Keywords— Brain Stroke, Decision Tree, Machine Learning, Stroke Prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

The brain controls growth, development, and a few bodily processes as the body's command center. It is an essential part of the neurological system. The brain can be impacted by a variety of diseases and disorders, impairing a person's capacity to carry out daily functions. Strokes are one of these ailments, which appear when a blood artery in charge of supplying the brain with vital nutrients becomes obstructed or, less frequently, ruptures. The impacts that follow is frequently immediate and significant. Our brain can suffer damage from stroke. Speaking, understanding, seeing, having strength, feeling, and coordination issues can result from this. Dementia may develop if one or more strokes produce sufficient brain damage. Sometimes strokes can lead to seizures. When there is an interruption in the blood supply to the brain, whether from a blockage or an abrupt rise in brain bleeding, a stroke ensues. Strokes can come in two different varieties. When the blood supply to the brain is restricted, oxygen and nutrients cannot reach the brain and an ischemic stroke result. Brain cells start to degrade in minutes without these vital components. Hemorrhagic strokes, on the other hand, are caused by a sudden brain hemorrhage, which puts pressure on brain cells and causes damage to them. Strokes that are ischemic (less than 90%) and hemorrhagic (less than 90%) involve blood arteries that are clogged. Based on where in the brain the blockage or bleeding takes place, strokes are further categorized. Between 82% and 90% of strokes are caused by

factors that you can control such as high blood pressure, obesity, active inactivity, unhealthy diet, and smoking. According to World Health Organization (WHO), Neurological and neurodevelopmental disorders are highly prevalent on a global scale, particularly impacting low- and middle-income nations, which account for over 70% of the overall burden. Annually, approximately 9 million individuals succumb to neurological diseases, making them the leading contributors to disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). In order to predict strokes and determine their risk, machine learning (ML) is essential. Large data sets are analyzed to find patterns that might not be immediately obvious to human viewers. In the context of stroke prediction, ML models can make use of a variety of data sources, including as demographic details, medical histories, lifestyle factors, and imaging investigations, to calculate a person's probability of having a stroke. We trained the model using the machine learning technique Decision Tree based on the input features from the dataset.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. The study[1] investigates the use of various deep learning (DL) and machine learning (ML) techniques in predicting the incidence of strokes based on a variety of biological factors. Numerous classification approaches are used, each with a distinct set of advantages for the analysis: logistic regression, support vector machines, decision trees, random forests, naïve bayes, k-nearest neighbors, artificial neural networks (ANN), XGBoost, AdaBoost, and LightGBM. The paper performs a thorough comparative analysis of these algorithms using a wide range of evaluation metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC), which measures the model's discriminatory abilities. These metrics include accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve, which rates the model's discrimination skills. This thorough analysis offers a complete understanding of the advantages and disadvantages of each algorithm in the context of stroke prediction, providing insightful information for further study and prospective therapeutic applications.

2. The methodology utilized in this study[3] is Naïve Bayes Classification, a supervised learning method that makes the assumption that the properties of the data are unrelated to one another. Based on the input variables (physiological factors), the algorithm applies the Bayes theorem to determine the likelihood of the output variable (stroke). The algorithm selects the class with the highest probability as the final forecast. With an accuracy score of 82%, precision score of 79%, recall score of 85%, F1 score of 82%, and ROC curve of 82%, this algorithm's results show that it performs the best among the six algorithms used in the paper. The paper comes to the conclusion that, given the dataset, Nave Bayes Classification is the best algorithm for stroke prediction. The publication also creates web and flask applications to deploy the model and let users submit their input parameters and obtain the prediction outcome.

3. [2] The chance of a brain stroke is predicted by this approach using machine learning, which takes into account important inputs like gender, age, current health problems, and smoking behaviors. The curated dataset is then put through a battery of classification algorithms, with Random Forest ultimately being declared undoubtedly the best algorithm, earning an outstanding accuracy rate of 98.56%. The benefits of this study for predicting strokes are numerous. It performs an exhaustive analysis of several machine learning techniques, grounded in a concrete, real-world dataset. Additionally, BrainOK introduces a ground-breaking strategy that enables users to identify their stroke vulnerability and take preventative action. The study also pushes the boundaries of data-driven healthcare solutions by demonstrating the effectiveness of machine learning in healthcare.

III. PROPOSED MODEL

In this study, a predictive model was created to determine the probability that a person would have a brain stroke based on a variety of input characteristics, including gender, age, hypertension, heart disease, marital status, type of employment, location, glucose level, body mass index, and smoking history. The dataset was trained using a variety of machine-learning techniques, and the results were carefully analysed to ascertain the best strategy for predicting brain strokes. By presenting the achieved accuracies from each algorithm, the comparative analysis of each approach is made clear. Figure 1 shows a schematic depiction of the suggested model. The first stage of the procedure entails gathering the data, which is then rigorously pre-processed to provide a refined dataset free of null or duplicate values, improving training and accuracy. Then, using data visualization approaches, patterns, trends, and outliers can be more easily found by giving the dataset a clear representation through graphical representations. The dataset is divided into training and testing subgroups to help with prediction, and these subsets are then fed into several categorization models. The model accuracies and evaluation metrics, such as the

confusion matrix, are calculated to determine the most effective prediction method.

1. System Flowchart

Fig 1: Flowchart Of Proposed System Design

The Kaggle website was used to obtain the dataset for this research. It consists of a numbered table with rows and columns that are structured. The table includes a few characteristics, such as gender, age, hypertension, heart disease, marital status, kind of job, type of residence, average level of glucose in the blood, body mass index (BMI), and smoking status. These characteristics play a key role in determining the propensity for a stroke to occur. In this research, the predictive model was fully trained using the dataset.

	gender	age	hypertension	heart_disease	ever_married	work_type	residence_type	avg_glucose_level	bmi	smoking_status	stroke
0	Male	67.0	0	1	Yes	Private	Urban	228.69	36.6	formerly smoked	1
1	Male	80.0	0	1	Yes	Private	Rural	105.92	32.5	never smoked	1
2	Female	49.0	0	0	Yes	Private	Urban	171.23	34.4	smokes	1
3	Female	79.0	1	0	Yes	Self-employed	Rural	174.12	24.0	never smoked	1
4	Male	81.0	0	0	Yes	Private	Urban	186.21	29.0	formerly smoked	1
	gender	age	hypertension	heart_disease	ever_married	work_type	residence_type	avg_glucose_level	bmi	smoking_status	stroke
4976	Male	41.0	0	0	No	Private	Rural	70.15	29.8	formerly smoked	0
4977	Male	40.0	0	0	Yes	Private	Urban	191.15	31.1	smokes	0
4978	Female	45.0	1	0	Yes	Govt_job	Rural	95.02	31.8	smokes	0
4979	Male	40.0	0	0	Yes	Private	Rural	83.94	30.0	smokes	0
4980	Female	80.0	1	0	Yes	Private	Urban	83.75	29.1	never smoked	0

Fig 2: Dataset for Brain Stroke Prediction

2. Data Preprocessing

Preparing the dataset for predictive modeling required multiple crucial phases in the data pretreatment procedure. First, assuming the dataset was kept at a certain file path, it was loaded from a CSV file. To make them compatible with machine learning algorithms, categorical variables such as gender, marital status, work type, residence type, and smoking

status were transformed into numerical format. Similarly, changes were performed on additional categorical variables. For example, gender was encoded as 1 for 'Male', 2 for 'Female', and 0 for any other value. Then characteristics were defined, except for the stroke column, and stroke was declared as the target variable. To make it easier to evaluate the model, the data was then divided into training and testing sets. To enable it to learn patterns from the features and produce precise predictions regarding stroke risk, a Decision Tree Classifier was finally instantiated and trained on the training data. Preprocessing procedures played a crucial role in guaranteeing that the data was suitably structured and prepared for training and evaluating machine learning models.

3. Data Visualization

It is simpler to understand statistics when they are presented as clear graphs or maps. A pie chart is a circular statistical graphic that is divided into slices to illustrate numerical proportions. The pie charts in the script visually represent the proportions of stroke cases within different categories of variables. These charts offer a clear and concise summary of the distribution of stroke cases among different groups. This visual information can be valuable in understanding the relative impact of different attributes on the occurrence of strokes. Figures: 3,4,5,6,7 all show the occurrence of stroke in that category. The Fig 8. Shows the overall stroke occurrence in the data.

Fig 5: Pie Chart of Stroke in Heart Disease

Fig 6: Pie Chart of Stroke in Residence Type

Fig 3: Pie Chart of Stroke in Gender

Fig 7: Pie Chart of Stroke in Smoking Status

Fig 4: Pie Chart of Stroke in Hypertension

Fig 8: Pie Chart Showing Overall Stroke Occurrence

4. Data Splitting

The dataset is divided into dependent and independent features using the train test split function of the Python library. The dataset is split into two sections: 25% for testing and 75% for training. In other words, the machine learning model will be trained using 75% of the original data, while its performance will be assessed using only 25% of the data. Stroke is a dependent feature, whereas all of the input characteristics—such as gender, age, BMI, smoking status, and so forth—are independent features.

5. Classification

The Decision Tree algorithm is a versatile and widely used machine learning technique for both classification and regression tasks. It works by recursively partitioning the input space (feature space) into regions, with each region corresponding to a specific prediction label or value. This partitioning is done based on the values of the features, which are selected in a way to maximize the predictive power of the resulting tree.

IV. CONCLUSION

The development of a strong machine-learning model specifically for early stroke diagnosis represents a major advancement in medical research. This ground-breaking device has the potential to significantly reduce the severity of strokes and, in the end, save lives by facilitating prompt intervention. This model is positioned to transform stroke diagnosis by utilizing machine learning to provide a prompt and precise risk assessment. The suggested method has determined the best stroke prediction algorithm through a thorough analysis of ML model. This accomplishment represents a significant advancement in the treatment and results of stroke patients.

V. FUTURE WORKS

Future research on stroke prediction will focus on refining the model by incorporating advanced features and integrating wearable technology for real-time monitoring. Longitudinal studies will provide insights into evolving risk factors.

Validation across diverse populations and telemedicine integration will enhance accessibility. Combining different data modalities and ensuring ethical data handling is critical. Integration into clinical decision support systems and patient education will empower healthcare professionals and individuals. Streamlined implementation within healthcare systems, including training, will be prioritized for widespread adoption and improved patient outcomes

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